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Impact Factor: 0.98

**GLASS CEILING –A REVIEW OF LITERATURE AND A
THEORETICAL PERSPECTIVE
(WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO WOMEN WORK-
FORCE)**

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ABSTRACT

"The Glass Ceiling" refers to an invisible barrier that limits the level to which a woman or another member of a demographic minority can advance within the hierarchy in an organization. In general, it is an attitudinal or organizational bias, which prevents women from occupying leadership positions in organizations. "Ceiling" stresses the limitation of upward progress of women is subjected to and "Glass" refers to the fact that through the limitation is apparently not written in any rule book, it is nevertheless a defeated fact understood by both the sexes. The glass ceiling metaphor has often been used to describe invisible barriers ("glass") through which women can see elite positions but cannot reach them ("ceiling"). These barriers prevent large numbers of women and ethnic minorities from obtaining and securing the most powerful, prestigious, and highest-grossing jobs in the workforce (wiki, 2015).

The history of India shows a very partial attitude towards women at all sections and levels in the society and workplace. Although a lot about women empowerment and equality of genders has been said and proposed but still the picture is ugly. The urban women are no exception to this phenomenon. The curiosity to understand this concept and gaining more insights for further detailed study led the authors to exploring the current review on literature related to this particular concept.

Objective- The present paper attempts to study the existing literature on this topic and to understand its theoretical perspective with giving its own findings and suggestions.

Design / Methodology/ Approach- This research work is of exploratory nature. The present research paper is conceptualized and is based on secondary data collected from various resources like books, news papers, management journals and internet.

Findings- Women are an important resource. Their competencies and abilities are precious and need to be wisely accounted for. Effective utilization of women workforce is needed for winning the global competition. Of course there are barriers but a change can be brought about in order to develop and utilize women's talents more for their mutual benefit. There are several cases where women were successful because of the interplay of organizational and family support, coupled with the individual drive for success, each woman demonstrated.

Conclusion: There is a persistable scope for women to excel in the corporate sector, if they learn to balance several resources like time, ideas, finance and relationships.

Limitations- Present research is conceptualized and based on secondary data; research could have been more authenticated if it would have been based on primary data.

Practical implications- This paper can inspire managers and experts of their fields for bringing certain changes in their view towards female work force in order to utilize their capabilities effectively for a better future.

KEYWORDS: Glass Ceiling, Women Empowerment, Gender Inequality, Leadership, Barriers in Career Advancement.

INTRODUCTION-

The term "Glass Ceiling" was coined in a 1986 Wall Street Journal Report on Corporate Women by Hymowitz and Schellhardt. The invisible barrier affects working women the most as it diminishes any chances of

advancement for someone who is career conscious such discrimination leads women to have feelings of low self-esteem, decreased motivation and slowing down of interest in their jobs.

The very fact of women being adequately represented in the work-force, but hardly present in the managerial positions got labeled “the glass ceiling”, “a barrier so subtle that it is transparent, yet so strong that it prevents women and minorities from moving up in the management hierarchy”(Morrison & Von Glinow (1990; p. 200). In 1991 The Glass Ceiling Commission was established and the U.S. Department of Labor defined "those artificial barriers based on attitudinal or organizational bias that prevent qualified individuals from advancing upward in their organization into management-level positions" as Glass Ceiling.

According to Wikipedia in Economics, the term **glass ceiling** refers to the scene, yet unbreakable barrier that keeps minorities and women from rising to the upper rungs of the corporate ladder, regardless of their qualifications or achievements”.

Initially, the metaphor applied to barriers in the careers of women but was quickly extended to refer to obstacles hindering the advancement of minority men, as well as women.

David Cotter et al. defined four distinctive characteristics that must be met to conclude that a *glass ceiling* exists. A glass ceiling inequality represents:

1. "A gender or racial difference that is not explained by other job-relevant characteristics of the employee."
2. "A gender or racial difference that is greater at higher levels of an outcome than at lower levels of an outcome."
3. "A gender or racial inequality in the chances of advancement into higher levels, not merely the proportions of each gender or race currently at those higher levels."
4. "A gender or racial inequality that increases over the course of a career."

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The present study was carried out with the objective of enhancing the knowledge vistas on the glass ceiling and its effects in Indian corporate sector with special reference to women workforce. The primary objective was to gather extensive knowledge of this topic so as to develop a better understanding towards its implications and roles. The secondary objective was to prepare a foundation for the future research in this area. This research work is of exploratory nature. The present research paper is conceptualized and is based on secondary data collected from various resources like books, news papers, management journals and internet.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE:

- **Carol Hymowitz and Timothy D. Schellhardt (March 24, 1986) Article in the Wall Street Journal.** “The Glass Ceiling: Why Women Can’t Seem to Break the Invisible Barrier That Blocks Them from the Top Job. They were the first to use this term. The term resonated with women around the world because it captured their frustrations and the term “glass ceiling” has now become commonplace.
- **Morrison and Von Glinow (1990)**, They defined Glass Ceiling as a barrier so subtle that it is transparent, yet so strong that it prevents women and minorities from moving up in the management hierarchy. According to Morrison women often fail to career plan and to build networks and have effective mentoring relationships which affect their advancement, they have been socialized to subordinate their careers in favour of home life and family (Fagenson and Jackson 1993).
- **Cox & Harquail, 1991; Olson, Frieze, & Good, 1987; Strober, 1982; Wallace, 1989; Wood, Corcoran, & Courant, 1993.** In a number of longitudinal studies that track comparably qualified men and women, such as graduates of the same MBA program or law school, it has been shown that over time there is degradation of the women's compensation that cannot fully be explained by differences in qualifications, work history, experience, or career interruptions. Women are more likely to choose jobs

based on factors other than pay, for instance: health care and scheduling that can be managed with the duties of primary care of children for which women are still overwhelmingly responsible, and thus they may be less likely to take jobs that require travel or relocation or jobs that are hazardous.

- **Connell (1987) and Sinclair (1998)** state that it's the gendered structures and practices operating within organizations which result in very different career experiences and outcomes for women and men, and the most senior organizational positions is considered as sites of hegemonic masculinity.
- **Adler (1999) and Sinclair (1999)** mention that in the USA and Australia there continues to be a significant difference in the numbers of men and women who reach senior management positions. However it is not the case in the junior and middle management position. Talmud and Izraeli 1999 opine that the number of women is increasing at junior and middle management positions.
- **Davidson and Cooper (1992)**, emphasize that men are viewed as leaders in organizations, while women are seen to be the followers. They argue that women who work in male-dominated environments are less inclined to see themselves as leaders or seek leadership roles. Davidson and Cooper found that managerial women experience greater strain, and feel more isolated at work, than do their male counterparts. This extra pressure manifests itself in issues such as lack of self-confidence and less obvious forms of discrimination causing these women to believe that they occupy minority status in their organizations and in society as a whole. This discrimination can be subtle, such as a lack of job advancement opportunities, a lack of mentors, or being presented with only stereotypical female worker challenges.
- **Lyness and Thompson (1997)**: Their studies reveal one consequence of sex stereotypes is that women's achievements tend to be devalued or attributed to luck or effort rather than ability or skill, and therefore this stereotype has the potential to reduce the organizational awards that they receive.
- **Asplund (1998)**, Answering the question why women in management do not advance as quickly as men he explains the following reasons : 1) Women did not receive the same training as available to men that was needed to lead to promotions and were not supported to attain the training; (2) Women started in positions that were not "promotion" tracks hence they were at a disadvantage from their time of entrance into the workplace; and, (3) Achievements of women managers were not recognized or appreciated to the same extent as men. In addition, (4) Women were not supported by their families to progress through their companies; (5) Women did not take risks like men did; and, (6) Women did not really want the promotion because of all the stress involved with the additional responsibility.
- **(Brown & Irby, 1998; Czaja, 1998)** believe that it is because of the balancing act that women struggle throughout their careers. Women sometimes choose to take a break temporarily to begin a family or care for a family since these duties are still expected to be primary responsibility of women. When they return, after the break, they continuously try to catch-up to their counterparts, never quite reaching it; hence missing out on the promotion track. Women who also try to balance career and family eventually reach a point where they halt their climb on the ladder to success fearful of not being able to balance all of the pressures or in some cases, just decide juggling between work and home is no longer worth the additional stress to them.
- **Tharenou (1999)**, According to him, women in most countries plateau at lower to mid level management positions. He agrees that one of the major explanations for women's lack of career advancement relates to the perceived lack of skill and knowledge. Tharenou believes that investments in the person and their skill development lead to increased remuneration and role status but because women make fewer investments than men they gain fewer rewards. In this context women are seen to lack the expertise and skill set required for senior management roles.
- **Baxter and Wright (2000)**: The core principles of a glass ceiling align with a contemporary movement to diversify senior-level positions in society by making advancements with regards to gender and racial/ethnic participation. Specifically, the concept of glass ceiling is generally viewed as a set up of impediments and/or barriers to career advancement for women or people of color.
- **Margaret Gibelmans (2000)** in his work on employees of 74 non-profit agencies throughout the United States indicates that females are overrepresented in direct-service positions. His studies "substantiate the existence of the glass ceiling phenomenon among the agencies .He states that men are

disproportionately represented in management, particularly upper-level management, and they earn higher salaries than women at all hierarchical levels of the organization."

- **Cotter et al. (2001):** He proposed a four- prong empirical test to measure for the existence of a Glass Ceiling. These four criteria inform our conceptualization of a glass ceiling effects and give structure to the current inquiry. In fact, cotter et al.'s (2001) work formed the basis of other studies seeking to understand glass ceiling effects as well (e.g., Maume, 2004). First, a glass ceiling must represent a gender or racial difference that is not explained by other job-relevant characteristics of the employee. Second, a glass ceiling effect is greater a higher levels of an outcome rather than lower levels. Third, glass ceiling effects reside in the chances of advancement into higher levels. Lastly, a disparity represents differences in advancement and opportunity that increase over the course of a career.
- **Cooper Jackson (2001)** emphasizes that organizations would still prefer a male-oriented management style where aggressive and direct behaviour is the norm. Schein (2001) suggests that men still believe that men are more likely than women to possess skills and characteristics required for management roles, whereas women perceive that women and men are equally likely to possess requisite
- **Cotter, Hermsen, Ovadia, & Vanneman,(2001);Maume,(2004):** It has been noted by these scholars that a glass ceiling occurs when discrimination increases in severity with movement up the occupational hierarchy.
- **Thomas Hunt and Philips (2004):** [Gender Inequality](#) is often embedded within the social hierarchy and this affects how women and men are perceived in leadership roles. Different traits are ascribed to females when compared to males that often color the selection process with unfounded bias. Therefore, possessing expertise is not viewed as positively as it is for males. This also suggests that lack of skills is not the only reason why women are not deemed worthy of leadership roles.
- **Lyness and Heilman (2006):** They found that in a study conducted with 448 upper-level employees that women were less likely to be promoted than males, and if they were promoted they had stronger performance ratings than males. However, performance ratings were more strongly connected to promotions for women than men. This suggests that women had to be highly impressive to be considered eligible for leadership roles, whereas this was not the case for men.
- **Alice H. Eagly and Linda L. Carli (2007):** Article in the Harvard Business Review. "Is there really a Glass Ceiling for Women?" Many women have inquired about whether or not an invisible barrier (or glass ceiling) exists just beneath the top of the corporate ladder that blocks successful women from achieving the highest rungs. According to them the answer is no, however, the sum of many obstacles along the way often hold women back from making it into the C-suite.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE: The Indian Picture

In India not many studies have been done on the challenges and opportunities faced by women in management jobs. However there are a set of literature which dwell on the aspect of glass ceiling faced by women managers in their career growth. These literatures reflect upon the low representation of women in management jobs and examine the factors that contribute such a state.

- **Ashok Gupta and Koshal (2001)** insist that the tussle created by motherhood and career ambition is known to affect women's career. The inhibiting factors include reluctance to travel, getting transferred and living away from families remains a significant barrier. Added it is women's exclusion from informal networks which also make them lose out opportunities for promotion.
- **Vimolwan Yukongdi and John Benson in the book "Women in Asian Management"** have spelled out the factors that inhibit women's growth. They also attribute women's slow growth to mainly individual and societal factors. They agree with Kulkarni (2002) who in his study "Women and Professional Competency" states that it is the traditional and cultural inhibitions acquired by women from childhood, nurtured by parents and reinforced by socialization which is the key hurdle that inhibited their urge to be in the executive or leadership position. This is further supplemented by lack of self direction, independence and self motivation.

- **Author Usha Kiran Rai** in her research paper “**Women Executives and the glass ceiling: Myths and Mysteries from Razia Sultana to Hillary Clinton**” concluded her views as under...
According to her research, in India the status of women has long been contradictory. Across the world, including the most developed nations; women are not to be seen in the top positions in the corporate sector. Despite the fact that 68 women have led their countries as presidents and prime minister, there still exist many barriers in the career path of women leading to leadership positions. Some of the barriers are related to the women themselves, and some to their organizations. They examined these barriers, and consider what can be done to facilitate a faster pace of change, in order to develop and utilize women’s talents more for their mutual benefit. Gradually, women managers in India have been successful in rising to top positions in Indian organizations, despite a culture that might suggest otherwise. These women were successful because of the interplay of organizational and family support, coupled with the individual drive for success, each woman demonstrated. They concluded that there is a persistable scope for women to excel in the corporate sector, if they learn to balance several resources like time, ideas, finance and relationships.
- **Pawan S. Budhwar, Debi S. Saini, and Jyotsna Bhatnagar** in their work „Women in Management in the New Economic Environment: The Case of India“ argue that historically, women in India have not enjoyed a good status in workplace settings whether in managerial or operative roles. The biggest challenge they face today is balancing dual role of organizational managers and housewives and the differential treatment meted out to them at work, which upholds the centrality and superiority of men. Due to stereotypes they are offered less challenging jobs and are often not involved in tackling crucial organizational issues.
- **Sanghamitra Buddhapriya** in her study „Women in Management“ states that women in the senior management positions are highly underrepresented. In India, she says although women have entered management since decades yet it is surprising to know that there is no government sponsored systematic data ascertaining the number of women in management in India. She states that in the Public sector units where some data exists it is disheartening to know that women are grossly underrepresented.

Existence of Glass Ceiling

The “glass ceiling” faced by women exists across all countries and is most evident at higher executive levels, particularly at the most senior level where female chief executives are very rare (**Oakley 2000**). A.P. Kitts’s study conducted on women in management in shows that despite the increase in the number of women intake in business schools only a small percentage of women are found in managerial positions and their entry into the managerial ranks is much lower compared to that of their male counterparts. Even when we look at an advanced country like UK, there is gender discrimination in the workplace. According to **Eyring and Stead (1988)** in the Metropolitan District Council situated in Yorkshire, UK where 66 percent of the workforces were women, majority of them occupied the lower range of the white collar posts. **Gibelmans (2000)** in his work on employees of 74 non-profit agencies throughout the United States indicates that females are overrepresented in direct-service positions. His studies "substantiate the existence of the glass ceiling phenomenon among the agencies .He states that men are disproportionately represented in management, particularly upper-level management, and they earn higher salaries than women at all hierarchical levels of the organization."

STATISTICS

Here are some of the recent surveys that reveal Women’s Low Representation in Management jobs

The study by Koshal, et al (2006), states that in India 2 women per 100 economically active men take administrative and managerial positions in India. The Confederation of Indian Industry released a study “Understanding the Levels of Empowerment of Women in the Workplace in India” covering 149 large and medium size companies across regions, which highlights that women comprise 16 percent at junior management level, 4 percent each at middle and senior levels and only 1 percent in organizational leadership positions (CEOs). According to the International Business Owners Survey (IBOS) 2004 by Grant Thornton30, 42% (59%

globally) of business in India include women in senior management positions, but women occupy 12% (19% globally) of the senior management posts available.

As a matter of fact, few Indian companies have women in senior management positions. Recent survey reveals that only 26.1% of the listed companies (392 of 1500 firms) have women on their boards. Out of the 278 directors of the BSE listed companies, there are only 10 women directors. Despite this, women executives in India earn 40% less than what men earn in their entire career. Even when compared to its global counterparts, corporate India stands below average. It is surprising to note that, only 36% of Indian companies have women top management positions, as compared to 91% of companies in China. This is an eye opening fact to contemplate on how successful women have been breaking the glass –ceiling.

For women's economic participation, India ranked 124th, (towards the bottom of the 136 countries listed in the 2013 *Global Gender Gap Index*), and for women's educational opportunity a ranking of 120.

Women in Management

- According to the latest Grant Thornton's International Business Report, 40% of businesses worldwide have no women in senior management, a figure that has remained unchanged since 2004.
- Women are just 3% of legislative, management, and senior official positions.
- In 2010, Women held only 5.3% of board directorships of BSE-100 companies.
- 22.6% of women are employed in business and they make up 14% of senior management roles.

Hierarchical Positions of the female labor force

According to Gender Diversity Benchmark, 2011, India has the lowest national female labor force and the worst leaking pipeline for junior to middle level position women.

- 28.71% of those at the junior level of the workplace
- 14.9% of those at the middle level
- 9.32% of those at the senior level.

The ASSOCHAM study reveals that educated metros and large town females are opting for self employment. Women are very well informed still denied promotions and better career prospects and amply face gender biases. It asserts that there is a need for a National Policy for promoting women in top levels of management. Only 3.3% of women are elevated to key positions while 78.9% continues to slog at humble positions and 17.7% of them despite working very hard are able to end up their career at middle management cadre.

Barriers Faced by women in Management Jobs in India

The ASSOCHAM study cites certain reasons as to why women lose out in their career. Those reasons are more to do with individual and societal factors that impinge on their career growth. It highlights that unlike men working women cannot stay on late at work and do networking and liaison, which helps in job promotions. Women resist mobility as they find it difficult to travel with home responsibilities and are not eager to take a transfer and job promotion for family reasons and remain satisfied with their current position. Health problems, gender discrimination and possessive husbands have been identified as other prominent factors obstructing growth prospects of career women. She emphasizes that low proportion of women in high ranks may be a reflection of prejudices, discriminatory recruitment policies, or lack of career orientation and lack of career commitment on the part of women in general.

Catalyst (1990) a consultant firm in women's employment surveyed CEOs and personnel officers at 1000 leading companies and found that women hold a quarter to half of management jobs at 22 percent companies but they have less than 5 percent of top management spots.

A recent update of a classic ILO study „Breaking through the glass ceiling: Women in management shows, that women's share of top positions remains low and the rate of progress discouraging. What the update revealed is that the number of women in top management jobs has only increased by between 1 and 5 percent over the past five years in some 33 countries surveyed. Lind Wirth, Director of the ILO Bureau for Gender Equality states that only a handful of women are making headlines here and there as they break through, but statistically they represent a mere few percent of top management jobs. Despite a few crack here and there these studies reveal that women's progress through managerial ranks is held back due to various factors. Various literatures have focused on the barriers that retard women's growth.

Barriers to Women's Advancement

Today although women's entry into management profession has increased yet their climb to the top, within various types of organizations, has not been smooth. The number of women that actually reach the top dwindles. But why is this? What happens to women as they begin to climb the corporate ladder to success? Why are they not making it to the top? They are confronted with very complicated challenges. The following sections of this literature review highlights several studies focused on the barriers women face in the in management jobs. These barriers could be individual and social or organizational .It could also be combination of all.

Individual or Societal Factors

Early research examining women's representation in senior management primarily focused on explaining the personal or the situation of the women managers. Riger and Galligan (1980) argue that the causal explanations for the lack of women in senior positions are either individual or the situational. Individual centered explanations suggest that the socialization processes experienced by women encouraged the development of personality traits, behaviours and attitudes that are contrary to the demands of a management role. And personality traits and behaviour differences are presented as a rationale for low representation. Accordingly women are seen to lack the confidence and assertiveness required for a management role, to be reluctant to apply for roles and to have lower aspirations and inappropriate expectations, about their capacity to combine family and work successfully (Spero 1987).

Organizational Factors

While the above literatures have emphasized upon individual factors being the reasons behind women manager's slow career growth, there are other studies that stress on organizational factors impacting women's career development. These studies argue that the organizational work environment, rather than individual characteristics, is the cause of women's low representation. One such study has been done by Kanter (1977) who argues that organizational policies and processes hamper career advancement for women and not their individual reasons. Kanter insists that women's positions in organizations can be understood in terms of organizational structures and the clustering of women in lower power roles rather than simply a function of individual gender difference. Kanter believes that had there been greater sharing of power within organizations, women would not have as much difficulty accessing management roles. Kanter suggests that the gender ratios at upper levels affect interactions between men and women. Men being the dominant group amplify the differences between them and women resulting in negative outcomes for women including performance pressures, exclusion from interaction with male peers, and stereotyping as women rather than as managers. There is also a suggestion that women may not necessarily help each other in breaking through the glass ceiling. The "queen bee syndrome" is used to identify those women who have reached the top, usually in a male environment, and who then adopt a counter militancy approach that is based on their own professional and social success (Rindfleish 2000). Davidson and Cooper (1986) and Harlan and Weiss (1982) also note that female managers report that they have to perform better than their male colleagues to prove themselves. Similarly Ragins (1998) report that women believe that they have to exceed performance targets and need to over-perform to counter negativity based on gender. As women are promoted and achieve senior executive roles, their visibility and profile increases and there is a perception of a greater requirement for them to perform better than their male counterparts (Klenke 1996).

Combination of Individual, Social and Organizational Factors Fagenson (1986) argues that there is a third way of explaining women's low representation in management This approach brings together the individual and organizational structural approaches. Davidson and Burke (1994) also suggest that there are a number of factors that maintain gender inequity in organizational leadership including formal and informal structures, economic, social and individual practices and behaviours. Tharenou (1999) holds a similar view on women's lack of career progression. She believes that specific but different factors move across both the individual and the organization which may facilitate or hinder advancement to higher management levels.

Research by Book (2000) found that few women, who climbed to the top rungs of the corporate ladder, did so at a heavy price to their perceived femininity. Often, women found that to be successful they had to adapt to male-inspired dress codes. Their rank, or position, within the organization became their primary source of respect just as it has been true for their male peers. Winning at any cost became the mantra of these women trying to fit into the "good old boy" network, and females who wanted to advance up the corporate ladder had to assume male methods to excel because of the many negative stereotypes associated with their own gender (Book, 2000). Further, Book suggests that stereotypes still persist and female managers who employ a "feminine style" of management will have trouble succeeding in the workplace.

CONCLUSION

The review of literature on “glass ceiling” with special reference to women workforce across the countries and in India shows that there are certain universal features apart from the cultural attributes and specificities for which there is so low representation of women in management jobs. Some of the barriers are related to the women themselves, and some to their organizations.

There is a gradual increase in number of women in the managerial jobs across the countries. Increase in number in women’s education, changing socio-cultural values, increasing awareness and consciousness about women’s rights and need for supplementary incomes are some of the reasons. However there is still an under - representation of women in managerial jobs not only in India but also across countries world over. Most of the women managers hold lower and middle management positions and the number of women remains extremely small in top management positions. The major barriers which restrict women to enter into managerial jobs are at individual, societal and organizational levels. Factors that restrict women managers to reach the top echelon are blocked opportunity, lack of support of employers, limited access to information, restricted access to training , marriage and motherhood , conflict between career and family responsibilities, prioritization of family over career, immobility of women and stereotypical attitude towards women managers. In the organizational structures discrimination against women managers exist relating to remuneration, job allocation, performance appraisal, promotion, training opportunities and reward structures.

The management qualities termed “feminine” are present in successful male as well as female leaders. We need to focus on the task at hand and not gender. For helping the females to climb the top ladder the organizations should start Mentorship and sponsorship programs, networking forums with successful women leaders should be conducted, support groups for the female employees should be made, programs to enable smooth on boarding of women who have taken career breaks. On the other hand, the sense of familial duty and support helps women get back on track after a hiatus. Thus, the ceiling is breachable only with increased awareness and empowerment of the leaders of tomorrow.

Finally we'll look at some exemplary examples of businesswomen who have managed to break through the so called glass ceiling.

Angela Braly	Director, President, CEO, WellPoint	2007 – Present
Carly Fiorina	CEO, Hewlett-Packard	1999 – 2005
Andrea Jung	Chairman, CEO, AvonProducts	1999 - Present
Sallie Krawcheck	CEO, Citigroup Global Wealth Management Division	2007 - 2008
Ann Mulcahy	Chairman, CEO, Xerox	2001 - 2010
Indra Nooyi	Chairman, CEO, PepsiCo.	2006 - Present
Irene Rosenfeld	CEO, Kraft Foods	2006 - Present
Martha Stewart	Chairman, President, CEO, Martha Stewart Omnimedia	1997 - 2003
Margaret Whitman	President, CEO, eBay President, CEO, Hewlett-Packard	1998 - 2008 2011 - Present
Oprah Winfrey	CEO, HARPO Productions, Inc.	1986 - Present

This shows that the scope for change exists if the female employees are well supported by the organizations and on the personal front.

References:

- Hymowitz, C., & Schellhardt, T. (1986, March 24). The corporate woman: A special report. The Wall Street Journal, Section 4, 1D–24D.
- Morrison, A. M., White, R. P., & Von Velsor, E. (1987). Breaking the glass ceiling: Can women reach the top of America's largest corporations?. Reading, MA: Addison-Wesley.
- Morrison, A. M., & Von Glinow, M. A. (1990). Women and minorities in management. *American Psychologist*, 45(2), 200–208.
- Cotter, D. A., Hermsen, J. M., & Vanneman, R. (1999). Systems of gender, race, and class inequality: Multilevel analyses. *Social Forces*, 78(2), 433–460.
- Baxter, J., & Wright, E. O. (2000). The glass ceiling hypothesis: A comparative study of the United States, Sweden, and Australia. *Gender and Society*, 14(2), 275–294.
- Cotter, D. A., Hermsen, J. M., Ovidia, S., & Vanneman, R. (2001). The glass ceiling effect. *Social Forces*, 80(2), 655–681.
- Linda Wirth (2001) *Breaking through the glass ceiling*, chapter *Women at the top*, ILO, Geneva, p. 38-41
- Maume, D. J., Jr. (2004). Is the glass ceiling a unique form of inequality? Evidence from a random-effects model of managerial attainment. *Work and Occupations*, 31(2), 250–274.
- Koshal, Manjulika, Koshal, Rajindar K. & Gupta, Ashok (2006). Women managers in India: challenges and opportunities.
- In *Management in India: Trends and Transition*/edited by Herbert J. Davis, Samir R. Chatterjee and Mark Heuer. New Delhi, Response Books, 2006.
- Women cry bias at work. The Telegraph, Calcutta. Saturday, April 15, 2006
- Grant Thornton (2004). *International Business Owners Survey (IBOS)*. Available at www.grantthornton.ca/surveys/GT_IBOS_2004_.pdf
- Reddy, Y. "Women executives: Glass ceiling myths and mysteries": *HRM REVIEW*, 9(8), 2009(August): 41-43.
- Women executives and the glass ceiling : Myths and Mysteries from Razia Sultana to Hillary Clinton - www.academia.edu
- Kothari C.R-. "Research Methodology Methods and Technique"
- Newspapers – Times of India (www.ItsMyAscent.com)

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Some of the portion of this paper is taken from various sites and articles. The broad objective of this paper is to spread the knowledge regarding particular subject, publication is one of the initiative taken for fulfillment of this objective. There is no any monitory intention behind the publication.

- -Author's